

Impact of Algorithms and Big Data on Educational Field

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Abstract

Using the potential of big data in education is the best option for students and institutions to further effectively anticipate student data in this competitive environment. The primary benefit of the Machine Learning algorithm is its ability to handle massive amounts of data in order to improve student results, administrative measures, and teaching technology. Students now have a great opportunity to choose courses based on their interests through the global learning community, which offers learning opportunities beyond typical classroom settings. The influence of big data algorithms is examined in this study, along with the comparison of algorithms from the perspectives of many writers. Sample data is then used to test the accuracy of the algorithms' predictions of student grades, which range from internal marks to university grading system.

Keywords: *algorithms, big data, education, machine learning, prediction*